

A Deep Residual Neural Network for Semiconductor Defect Classification in Imbalanced Scanning Electron Microscope Datasets

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Abstract

The detection of defects using inspection systems is common in a wide range of corporations such as semiconductor industries. The use of techniques based on deep learning (DL) and, in particular, convolutional neural networks (CNNs), emerges as a powerful tool to classify aesthetic defects and other unwanted anomalies in industrial automation applications marked by their natural complexity and high degree of variability. In this paper, an effective hybrid deep residual neural network approach is presented which merges traditional computer vision techniques to perform an appropriate defect segmentation and a deep residual neural network-grid search-based hyperparameter optimization for defect classification. The proposed model has been compared with other baseline algorithms and with other hybrid methods-based CNNs using different performance metrics such as F1-score, Cohen's kappa coefficient, confusion matrix and computing time, on imbalanced datasets obtained from scanning electron microscope (SEM) images. The results obtained illustrate that the designed hybrid method provides the best defect classification of defects in semiconductor wafers in terms of F1-score (99.443%) while consuming the least computational time.

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Keywords: Deep Learning, Convolutional Neural Networks, Semiconductor Device Manufacturing, Inspection System, Defect Classification

1. Introduction

Reliability is a must in the semiconductor manufacturing industry [1, 2, 3], which keeps growing and gaining in relevance to the point that profit has been more than \$429 billion in 2019 according to STATISTA website [4]. Electronic devices play a major role in our daily lives. As a result, pursuing the maximum reliability is crucial for developing high quality products that increase both customer satisfaction and company revenues [5]. As electronic devices and their components become smaller, the size of a defect that totally ruins the functioning of the device also becomes smaller [6]. Therefore, it is increasingly necessary to install powerful and robust inspection systems such as SEM in the early stages of the manufacturing chain in order to detect those killer defects [7, 8, 9, 10, 11].

Nowadays, most inspection systems are guided by a human operator who must configure the inspection devices and classify the defects. However, human operators may incur in errors principally owing to visual fatigue and work stress and, consequently, increment additional costs [12]. In addition, traditional computer vision techniques are sensitive to the noises that characterize industrial environments and are therefore not fully reliable [13]. With the advent of artificial intelligence (AI) new techniques are complementing and even replacing human operators and traditional computer vision techniques to improve defect detection and classification [14, 15, 16, 17]. On the other hand, since large volumes of data are usually acquired during the inspection process, machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) are the AI techniques which must be highlighted. Both ML and DL can deal with large volumes of data and obtain relationships between them. In addition, DL-based technologies are achieving human-level classification performance [18]. Within DL technologies, CNNs offer good classification results when working with a sufficient volume of data as is the case of our proposed research [19, 20]. The classification performance of a CNN is intimately linked to the number and quality of images available. Furthermore, when there is an imbalance in the dataset such that the difference between the number of images of minority and majority classes is significant, obtaining good results in the classification task is a challenge [21].

There are few works in which CNNs fed with SEM images have been used in industrial applications related to semiconductor wafer manufacturing. For example, in [22], a self-designed CNN with different configurations has been built for detecting defective wafers after the sawing operation. In a recent approach [23], the authors have implemented different state-of-the-art CNNs which are combined with the Radon transform algorithm [24] to detect and classify defects in semiconductor wafers. In [20], the authors have created a CNN and combined it with a K-nearest neighbors (K-NN) algorithm to detect unknown classes and, in [25], CNNs have even been used to classify the chemical composition of particles in semiconductor wafers. However, to the authors' knowledge, there is no scientific literature which classify defects in semiconductor materials from a SEM image dataset as imbalanced as in this paper, [which seems incredible in the authors' opinion since SEM device is used all over the world and in all manufacturing industries, including the semiconductor one, data imbalance is a continuum as it is dependent on the periodicity of defects.](#) In order to cover this lack of knowledge, the objective of this research is to detect and classify up to seven different classes of defects in semiconductor wafers on imbalanced datasets obtained from SEM images, [contributing to the automation of the semiconductor industry and the resulting cost reduction and better working conditions.](#)

For this purpose, a truly effective hybrid deep residual neural network approach is presented which merges traditional computer vision techniques to perform an appropriate defect segmentation and a deep residual neural network-grid search-based hyperparameter optimization for defect classification. On the one hand, the problem of the dataset imbalance is solved by: (i) by applying data augmentation techniques to the original dataset [26, 27], obtaining enough images to train the CNN model; and, (ii) evaluating its performance by using an appropriate performance metrics [28]. On the other hand, the deep residual neural network, ResNet50 CNN model, is fine-tuned by means of a grid search algorithm-based hyperparameter optimization and the classification results achieved by the model are evaluated according to performance metrics such as the F1-score and the Cohen's kappa coefficient (κ), which are especially appropriate when classifying imbalanced datasets as it is the case. The effectiveness of the proposed approach has been evaluated and compared with other recent baseline algorithms found in the scientific literature in terms of statistical parameters as accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, Cohen's kappa coefficient (κ), confusion matrix and computation time showing that the proposed model has the best performance.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 is devoted to a detailed explanation regarding the background to the work. This section contains information on the data acquisition obtained by a SEM device, the original defects' dataset, the description of the different classes of defects considered, the challenge of dealing with imbalanced datasets and a brief description of the fundamentals of CNN residual networks. Section 3 sets out the different steps of the proposed methodology to carry out the detection and classification of the defects. Section 4 illustrates the experimental results obtained by the ResNet50 hybrid model following the proposed methodology. Then, the results achieved by the proposed hybrid deep residual neural network will be compared with those obtained with other baseline state-of-the-art CNN models and with those obtained in related works. Finally, Section 5 collects a series of conclusions and suggestions for future work.

2. Background

This section provides a brief description about some of the concepts used throughout the paper for its better understanding. In particular, the concepts treated in the paper that needs additional details are: (i) the SEM data acquisition process; (ii) the original dataset including information about the characteristics of the images and the count and description of the different defect classes; (iii) the problem about working with an imbalanced dataset and possible solutions to treat with it; and, (iv) an in-deep explanation about convolutional residual networks with a particular focus on the ResNet50 CNN model that will be used in the architecture of the proposed hybrid deep residual neural network solution developed in this work. The following subsections dealt with this.

2.1. SEM Data Acquisition

As defects are getting smaller and smaller due to the shrinkage of electronic devices, inspection devices must be more powerful to perform a proper defect detection along the entire inspection line. The principal parameter used to define the power of a visual inspection system is the resolution limit, which can be defined as the minimum distance at which two different objects are identified as independent [29]. For instance, the resolution limit of the human eye is around 0.1 mm and that of a light optical microscope is about 200 nm [30]. These resolution limits, which might be adequate for carrying out the visual inspection task in other industrial applications, are not

suitable for semiconductor defect detection. SEM devices, whose resolution limit ranges from 1 to 10 nm (depending on their settings), are appropriate for industrial applications which need a really high precision in the inspection task, as it is the case here.

Figure 1: Scanning electron microscope [31].

A typical SEM device consists of an electron gun, several lenses, an aperture, a scanning coil and an electron detector as illustrated in Figure 1. The electron gun is composed of a cathode, an anode and a Wehnelt cap. There are three types of electron guns: field emission, tungsten hairpin and lanthanum hexaboride (LaB_6) guns. The electron gun emits a beam of electrons which passes through the lenses of the condenser. These lenses just cause the beam to converge. Then, the aperture reduces and excludes extraneous electrons in the lenses. The scan coil then deflects the beam to scan the sample across the x -axis or y -axis. Finally, the interaction between the beam and the sample generates different signals that are then merged to form the SEM image thanks to the electron detector. Within these signals, back-scattered electrons (BSEs), secondary electrons (SEs), X-rays, auger

electrons and catholuminescence are those which provide the relevant information [32, 29, 33].

BSEs, released by the elastic interaction between the beam and the sample, are high-energy electrons that provide topological and compositional information about the sample [34, 29]. SEs, which results from the inelastic interaction between the sample and the beam, are low-energy electrons that provide information regarding the topography of the sample [34, 29]. Auger electrons are also low-energy electrons that are used to analyze in detail the sample’s surface chemistry [32]. X-rays provide chemical information of the sample [32, 29], while catholuminescence, apart from being a mechanism devoted to the energy stabilization task [29], can also be useful for revealing defects that degrade the radiating properties of the specimen [32].

2.2. Original Dataset

As mentioned in the previous subsection, the images used in this work have been captured by means of a SEM device along the early inspection stage of the wafer manufacturing chain. The original dataset, which were previously manually labeled by an expert and illustrated in Figure 2, were arranged in eight different classes whose description is found in Table 1 and whose distribution is included in Table 2. Note that, from Figure 2 and Table 1, one of the classes considered corresponds to images without defects.

Figure 2: Samples of the classes of defects considered.

Table 1: Description of the defect classes

Defect class	Description
No defect	This class does not contain defects. In fact, this class will be excluded from the dataset for the experiments.
Class 100	The defects of this class are elongated and tend to form a straight line across the entire image. The texture of the defect is very heterogeneous.
Class 150	The defects that belong to this class are like the ones of class 100. The main differences are the thickness of the straight line, which is thinner in class 150 and the texture of the defect, which is much more homogeneous also in class 150.
Class 200	Defects of this type are in the form of mounds and have a variable size and shape.
Class 300	Defects of this class are pits or cavities which have a characteristic hexagonal or pentagonal shape.
Class 350	These defects are identical to the ones in class 300, but there is more than one defect per image. The defects may even overlap with each other.
Class 500	Defects of this class consist of a pit or cavity with a mound inside it. Again, defects have a wide variety of sizes and shapes.
Class 550	Defects of this type have rounded shapes with different sizes.

Table 2: Distribution of images (original dataset)

Defect class	Count
No defect	227
Class 100	55
Class 150	8
Class 200	4,008
Class 300	1,068
Class 350	43
Class 500	289
Class 550	4

2.3. Data Imbalance

As can be observed from Table 2, there exists a huge imbalance between the different classes. The classification of the minority classes is therefore a big challenge. The imbalance can be solved in three different ways depending

on the number of images of the classes that conforms the dataset. The first strategy is *subsampling*, which consists of randomly removing images from the majority classes to obtain a given number of images from all classes. Obviously, this approach can only be used when there are enough images in the minority classes. The second strategy is *oversampling*, which consists of increasing the number of images in the minority classes to obtain a given number of images for each class. This oversampling is done by means of *data augmentation* techniques. Oversampling is the only solution when the number of minority class images is too low to train a model. Finally, the third approach would be a *mix between undersampling* for the majority classes *and oversampling* for the minority classes until an optimal number of images is obtained.

For this work, as the number of images for the minority classes is really low, the solution adopted is to oversample, addressing the challenge of imbalance by using data augmentation techniques to generate synthetic images [27]. The data augmentation approach is explained later in Section 3. In addition, apart from the application of data augmentation techniques, there are some specific metrics to evaluate models when dealing with highly imbalanced datasets. These metrics directly consider the number of instances of each class, which makes them ideal for application in work such as this. These metrics and their use are clearly detailed in Section 3.

2.4. Fundamentals of Convolutional Residual Networks

Reviewed literature [23, 35, 36, 37, 38] suggests that *residual networks* (ResNets) offer promising results in classification problems. Within these ResNets, *ResNet50* will be selected in this work as a potential candidate to develop the proposed hybrid method owing its excellent properties as it fuses both great results and low resource consumption compared to other ResNets [39]. Throughout this subsection, the general components of the CNN, ResNets approach and with a particular focus on ResNet50 architecture are briefly detailed.

CNNs are computational models inspired by the human visual cortex, which is the part of the brain in charge of the recognition task [40]. These models are composed of thousands of neurons arranged in different layers. Every neuron has an associated weight which is optimized by means of the backpropagation algorithm when training iteration after iteration. A typical CNN model architecture, at least, contains the following type of layers (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Basic CNN architecture.

- *Convolutional Layer* is usually used when the feature extraction process is carried out. The first layers extract low level features while high-level features are extracted in the last layers. Features are extracted through a convolution operation [41], which is the scalar product between an input tensor and the kernel or filter. The kernel or filter is a matrix that slides through all the input tensor and is composed of neurons and their weights. The weights are adjusted autonomously by means of the backpropagation algorithm, which aims to minimize the loss of the network along a series of iterations [42]. The result of this scalar product receives the name of feature map. Some of the convolutional layer parameters to be configured are the depth (number of kernels), the kernel size and the stride [43].
- *Activation Layer*. Real-world data are non-linear. Therefore, some non-linearity must be introduced to increase the performance of a CNN and to give the model the ability to generalize to real-world data once trained. This is the purpose of including activation layers in the model. The activation function decides whether or not a neuron is activated; that is, whether or not the neuron's input is relevant to the rest of the network. There are different activation functions used to introduce the non-linearity: sigmoid, hyperbolic tangent, Swish activation and rectified linear unit (ReLU), among others [44]. The choice of the activation function is of great importance to the performance of the CNN model. The functions can even be combined throughout the different layers of a model, being one more parameter to consider when developing your own CNN model.
- *Pooling Layer* is the layer where a subsampling or pooling operation is performed. This operation is performed in order to reduce the volume of data the network must deal with. Data volume reduction

saves considerable computing time [45]. The most commonly operations employed are max pooling, average pooling and mixed pooling, although others such as spatial pyramid pooling [46], stochastic pooling [47], spectral pooling [48] or multiscale orderless pooling [49] are being widely used. [The choice of pooling method directly influences the performance of the overall model.](#) Table 3 lists the main advantages and disadvantages of some of the classifiers mentioned [50, 51, 52].

Table 3: Impact of pooling strategy

Pooling Strategy	Advantages	Drawbacks
Max pooling	-Reduces computation time in upper layers of the CNN -Good combination with sparse distributions	-Is deterministic -Some features vanish if the elements present in the pooling region are high in magnitude
Average pooling	-Easy to understand and execute	-Is forthcoming -Low contrast if minor magnitudes are considered
Mixed pooling	-Avoids overfitting -Is stochastic	-The mix proportion does not adapt to the region's attributes once learned
Pyramid pooling	-Ability to adapt to any input size -Response to the image scales of an input -Spatial bins with multiple levels	-Complex implementation in the training of the CNN
Stochastic pooling	-Is stochastic -Not computationally complex -Lack of hyperparameters to specify -Compatible with regularization methods	-Difficult to interpret -Usually leads to overfitting -Difficult to scale

- *Fully-Connected Layer.* As its name reveals, the neurons that compose the fully-connected (FC) layers are connected to each of the neurons of the previous layer. In FC layers, the dimension of the input data is reduced to a $(1 \times 1 \times N)$ vector (feature vector of the whole image), [reason why these layers cannot be followed by another convolutional layer](#) [45]. Due to the interconnections of each neuron with those of the previous layers, all paths from input to output are considered, thus performing high-level reasoning leading to high-level feature extraction [53]. This type of layers groups the vast majority of the trainable parameters of the CNN [54]. In order to remove the connections to neurons whose

weight is equal to 0, reducing the computing time and enabling the system to be lighter, as well as preventing overfitting and boosting the performance, the dropout algorithm is a typical solution [55].

- *Classification Layer.* The input to this layer is a one-dimensional vector coming from the previous FC layer. The classification layer transforms each element of the vector into probabilities of belonging to a certain class. Then, in order to assign the most probable class to each element, the SoftMax function, which is the most used, rounds up to 1 the highest probability (the element belongs to that class) and rounds down to 0 the rest of the probabilities (the element does not belong to any of those classes).

Each combination of layers will result in a different CNN model. Looking at this, it can be concluded that there will be infinite combinations of layers and, therefore, infinite models. One of the well-tested CNN designs which has an excellent performance in classification tasks are residual networks (ResNets) [56], which have emerged as a revolution in the field of CNNs. ResNets were developed to solve the degradation problem of most deep CNN models. When deep CNN models start to converge, their accuracy becomes saturated and then suddenly drops off. Moreover, adding new layers does not improve the problem. In fact, it gets even worse. ResNets avoid degradation by including what are known as residual blocks. Residual blocks (RBs) obey the principle that it is easier to optimize a residual function referenced to the layer input than to directly optimize the original unreferenced function. In other words, each layer does not have to modify every weight of its neurons, but only learns a residual correction of the previous layer. To do this, each layer is connected to the next and features a short connection that skips two or three layers ahead [57]. Figure 4 illustrates how residual blocks work where x is the function that must be fitted, $F(x)$ denotes the output of the system after convolutions, $ReLU$ is the activation function used in this RB [39].

Finally, once explained the residual block approach, it is time to present the architecture of ResNets which is depicted in Figure 5. From the image, it can be appreciated that ResNet50 consists of 50 layers. This model is based in the previously explained residual block approach and it has 3.8×10^9 floating points operations. From Figure 5 the obtaining of the ResNet50 CNN model architecture contains the following elements:

- A convolutional layer with a kernel size of 7×7 and 64 different kernels,

Figure 4: Residual block.

all with a stride of size 2.

- Then, a pooling layer which implements a MaxPooling operation with a stride size of 2.
- The following convolutional layers are composed by a kernel size of 1×1 and 64 different kernels, following this by a kernel size of 3×3 and 64 different kernels and, at last, by a kernel size of 1×1 and 256 different kernels. These three convolutional layers are repeated in a total of 3 times so resulting in a total of 9 layers in this step.
- After that, the convolutional layers are composed by a kernel size of 1×1 and 128 different kernels, following this by a kernel size of 3×3 and 128 different kernels and, at last, a kernel size of 1×1 and 512 kernels. These three convolutional layers are repeated 4 times so resulting in 12 layers in this step.
- Then, the next convolutional layers are composed by a kernel size of 1×1 and 256 different kernels, following this by a kernel size of 3×3 and 256 different kernels and, at last, by a kernel size of 1×1 and 1024 different kernels. These three convolutional layers are repeated 6 times so resulting in a total of 18 layers.

- After that, the following convolutional layers are composed by a kernel size of 1×1 and 512 different kernels, following this by a kernel size of 3×3 and 512 different kernels and, at last, by a kernel size of 1×1 and 2,048 different kernels. These three convolutional layers are repeated 3 times so resulting in a total of 9 layers.
- Finally, a pooling layer which implements and average pooling following by a fully-connected layer containing 1,000 nodes and, finally, a classification layer which implements the SoftMax function.

To finish the ResNet50 CNN model description, it is important to note that the activation functions and the pooling layers did not count as a layer so, totaling this results in $1 + 9 + 12 + 18 + 9 + 1 = 50$ layers deep convolutional network.

Figure 5: ResNet architecture [58].

3. Methods

This section is centered in the explanation of the different steps in which the proposed methodology for detection and classification of defects in imbalanced datasets achieved with scanning electron microscopy images can be decomposed. The graphical illustration of the proposed hybrid method is depicted in Figure 6 and the different steps of the method will be treated in detail in the following subsections.

3.1. Data Acquisition and Image Preprocessing

Once the dataset has been constructed from the SEM images of wafer defects that were acquired during the inspection phase in the early stages of

Figure 6: Proposed hybrid deep residual neural network methodology for semiconductor detection and classification of defects through imbalanced datasets obtained from SEM images.

the wafer manufacturing chain, an image preprocessing stage is carried out. The aim of this task is to prepare and to normalize the SEM images obtained in the inspection phase. The preprocessing stage is a major phase in every

work related to CNN (see Figure 6). In our case, the input images must have a unique size and the same number of channels. The images of the original dataset are grayscale images (one channel) but there are two different image sizes. Therefore, a resizing operation has been performed by the application of the following image transformations:

- *Image resizing.* The original images of the dataset had two different sizes, 480×480 and 720×720 pixels. Therefore, all the images have been resized to 480×480 pixels to obtain a unique image size.
- *Image cropping.* The images have been cropped to prepare them for the synthetic image generation, removing the scale bar which appears at the bottom of each image (see Figure 2). All images have been cropped to a 400×400 pixels size.
- *Data splitting.* Once the original dataset has been normalized is now when the original dataset is divided into two subsets, as it is illustrated in Figure 7, one is for test purposes (10% of the original dataset) in which the images that compose the test set were not selected randomly, but following the same distribution as the original dataset, always making sure that all classes were represented in the test set. On the other hand, the remaining subset (90% of the original dataset) will be utilized in the synthetic image generation stage.

Figure 7: Data splitting procedure for training, validation and testing of the CNN model.

3.2. Synthetic Image Generation

Once the dataset is normalized, the next stage is to prepare and enhance the images for the subsequent training of the CNN model. The main objectives of this stage are the following: (i) prepare and enhance the images for training the deep residual neural network; and, (ii) increase the number of images in the dataset to improve the classification performance of the model. The synthetic image generation stage is carried out by concatenating the following image transformations (see Figure 6):

- *Defect segmentation.* The purpose of this image transformation is to separate the defect from its background with the aim to be able to apply image transformations to the defect instead of applying them to the whole image. Defect segmentation is done by means of a threshold and what we have called a conditioned addition. After applying the threshold, the defect will be black, and the background will be white. The conditioned addition consists of applying the following rule: if the pixel value of the binarized image is 255 (white color), it will be replaced by a 0 (black) and, if it is not 255, it will be replaced by the pixel value of the original image. The segmentation of the defect also helps to increase the performance of the model, as the CNN will focus on the defect itself, leaving aside the background, which will be uniform for all images. Defects in the test set images will also be segmented following the same procedure.
- *Data augmentation.* Image transformations such as rotation, translation, scaling and flipping are applied to the segmented defects in order to generate an additional set of synthetic images [27, 59]. Data augmentation helps to increase the diversity of the dataset for the training of the model without having to collect additional data [60]. The resulting augmented dataset distribution is illustrated in Table 4, in which it is observed that, although the augmented dataset is still imbalanced, the minority classes now contain enough images to train the subsequent CNN model and ensure an adequate performance after model tuning. The problem of the imbalanced dataset is therefore now almost negligible if the right metrics are used to assess the performance of the model.
- *Background addition.* With the purpose of generating images as close as possible to the original ones, a uniform background is added to the

Table 4: Distribution of images (augmented dataset)

Defect Class	Count
Class 100	2,205
Class 150	784
Class 200	4,008
Class 300	1,068
Class 350	1,716
Class 500	2,402
Class 550	394

resulting synthetic images. The background will also be added to the previously segmented images in the test set.

- *Data splitting.* After obtaining the augmented dataset, a division of the augmented dataset into two subsets is carried out (see Figure 7). The first subset (80% of the augmented dataset) is selected randomly from the augmented dataset and will be employed in the subsequent training process of the CNN model while the remaining subset (20% of the augmented dataset) will be used for validating the CNN model. This splitting approach was adopted according to the typical percentages recommended in the reviewed literature [20, 25, 61]: 60%-80% of the data for training, 10%-20% for validation, and 10%-20% for testing. Had the original dataset contained enough images, cross-validation would have been ideal for performing training, validation, and testing of our models. However, this has not been possible since the aim of this work was to perform the tests with original images and there are classes with a really low number of images. Therefore, the described splitting strategy has been adopted to start the training process of the models.

3.3. CNN Implementation

The next stage of the proposed methodology is the CNN implementation (see Figure 6). Here, the CNN model is trained, tuned, validated, tested and evaluated in accordance with the following learning strategy:

- *CNN-grid search-based deep neural network.* The proposed hybrid-based CNN model requires the selection of a set of optimal parameters (also

known as tuning or hyperparameter optimization) for its corresponding training and tuning process. Hyperparameters are defined as design parameters that influence in the evolution of the learning process and that need to be tuned for obtaining an optimal model and minimizing the loss function. In this research, we have relied on the use of the grid search method to find the tuple of hyperparameters that optimizes the model [62]. The grid search algorithm then trains the hybrid-based CNN model for a subset of hyperparameter space of the algorithm, followed by a performance metric. The grid search algorithm constructs a model on each parameter combination possible, leading to multiple iterations. The model combinations for every parameter are stored and the experiment which classify more accurate the different defects in the SEM images is then selected as having found the best tuple of hyperparameters [63]. Although this algorithm is not the most optimal in terms of computational time (it is computationally expensive), it is perfect for selecting the optimal combination of parameters within a set of predefined options. The different hyperparameters that are considered for the model’s tuning are listed below:

- The *batch size* is a hyperparameter which indicates the number of samples that will be considered for tuning before updating its internal model parameters. In summary, the batch size is the number of samples that are passed to the CNN in one go. Therefore, the larger the batch size, the lower the time consumption during model training. However, using an excessively high batch size could result in poor model performance in not being able to generalize to data not previously observed. It is a parameter that can be tuned during the training process.
- The *optimizer* is another hyperparameter included in the proposed grid search algorithm whose goal is to bridge the gap between updating the model parameters and the loss function. This goal is met by modifying the weights of the neurons in the network and playing with different learning rates to reduce the loss. There are many types of optimizers. Some of the most commonly used are RMSprop, Adamax, Adagrad, Adadelta, etc. However, the most popular optimizers are adaptive moment estimation (ADAM) [64] and stochastic gradient descent (SGD) [65].

- The *learning rate* (LR) is probably the most important hyperparameter when training the CNN model and whose objective is to determine how much the model weights change as a function of the error in the previous iteration. Typical values for LR range from 0 to 1. Large LR values lead to a great instability in the training phase, while excessively small ones would lead to training errors.
- The *loss function* is the last hyperparameter considered in the grid search in this work and whose aim is to determine how the error is calculated.

There are many other parameters that could be configured, especially if the purpose of this work was to develop a new CNN model. Some examples are the number and type of layers, the size of filters or masks in each layer, the pooling strategy or the activation functions used. In this work with commercial CNN models, their original architecture will be preserved, as will be discussed in Section 4.1.

- *Performance Metrics.* The performance of the models is evaluated with the help of a set of metrics. Performance metrics play a major role in classification problems where the aim is to discriminate between different DL algorithms, in order to facilitate the selection of the best algorithm according to the research objective [66, 28]. The metrics used in this research are described next.

- *Accuracy (ACR)* is defined as the level of closeness to the true value. It is calculated in terms of true positives (TP), true negatives (TN), false positives (FP) and false negatives (FN), and computed as follows:

$$ACR = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (1)$$

- *Precision (P)* is referred to the proportion of successful positive predictions. It is obtained as follows:

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (2)$$

- *Recall (R)* is defined as the ratio of relevant predictions; and is calculated as follows:

$$R = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (3)$$

- *F1-score* ($F1$) is defined as the harmonic mean between P and R [67]. It is one of the most appropriate metrics for evaluating models when training models with imbalanced datasets [68]. It is determined as follows:

$$F1 = \frac{2 \cdot P \cdot R}{P + R} \cdot 100 \quad (4)$$

- *Cohen’s kappa coefficient* (κ) is a measure of the degree of agreement between the values predicted by the model and the actual values [69]. It considers both the imbalance of the dataset and the effect of chance. Therefore, it is interesting for evaluating the models presented in this work. The Cohen’s kappa coefficient is calculated as follows:

$$\kappa = \frac{ACR_0 - ACR_e}{1 - ACR_e} \quad (5)$$

where ACR_0 denotes the overall accuracy of the model and ACR_e indicates the agreement between the actual class values and the model predictions by chance.

- *Confusion matrix* is a table or matrix which helps to visualize the performance of a certain model. The real labels of a class are arranged in rows and the predicted labels in columns of the matrix. This metric will be employed in Section 4 to visually compare the classification performance of ResNet50 against other state-of-the-art CNN models.

Note that most of these metrics are designed, by default, for binary classification problems. However, a multiclass problem can be broken down into a set of binary classification problems, one for each class present, following the one-versus-the-rest (OVR) approach. Thus, in a seven-class multiclass problem, the OVR divides it into seven different binary tasks. The final scores are obtained as an average of the score obtained on the binary tasks. There are three different ways to perform this averaging: macro-averaging, micro-averaging, and weighted-averaging. The macro-average involves a classical arithmetic average between the scores of each class. The micro-average is calculated in the same way as the accuracy, i.e. by dividing the correctly classified instances by the total. Finally, the weighted-averaging performs an arithmetic mean

that is weighted by considering the number of instances in each class. Probably, weighted-averaging is the most interesting approach to calculate the final scores, being this the way the multiclass evaluation metrics are calculated in this work. Within the aforementioned performance metrics, the performance indexes that are sensible to imbalance issues and, therefore, those which are more appropriate for the evaluation of models that work with imbalanced datasets are the F1-score and the Cohen’s kappa coefficient. These two performance metrics, together with the validation loss of the models, are selected for the model evaluation that is performed in Section 4.

4. Results and Discussion

Having described the methodology that has been followed for developing this work, it is time to present and discuss the results obtained. The experiments have been conducted with a workstation computer with the following hardware specifications: CPU Intel i7-10700KF v8 @ 3.80 GHz, 32 GB RAM, and NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2070 SUPER 8GB. Keras [70] and TensorFlow [71] libraries have been used to train the models, choosing Pycharm [72] as integrated development environment (IDE) and Python 3.8 [73] as the programming language. The grid search algorithm will be described in detail and the performance of the hybrid residual neural network based on ResNet50 CNN model will be discussed in terms of classification performance and computing time. In addition, the performance of proposed methodology will be compared with that of some state-of-the-art CNN models through confusion matrices of the different models, which will contribute to clearly visualize the obtained results. Finally, a comparison between the results obtained in our experiments and those achieved by similar works in terms of F1-score, accuracy and computing time metrics will be presented. The following subsections dealt with this.

4.1. Grid Search

As it was introduced in the Section 3.3, a grid search algorithm has been employed in order to tune the hybrid ResNet50 CNN model after the synthetic image generation step. Table 5 depicts the grid search hyperparameters considered for the study where it is observed that the grid search algorithm will operate for tuning the model with two main hyperparameters: the optimizer and learning rate (LR). Therefore, the combinations of those param-

eters are going to be analyzed. On the one hand, different optimizers will be used to train the model. As mentioned in Section 3.3, there are different optimizers that can be implemented in a CNN. However, including a large number of these optimizers in the grid search would exponentially lengthen the training time. Therefore, two optimizers will be introduced in this grid search, SGD and ADAM, both of which have played a primary role in many successful research experiments and DL projects.

Table 5: Grid search hyperparameters considered for hybrid ResNet50 tuning.

Hyperparameters	Values
Batch size	9
Loss function	CCE
Optimization	ADAM, SGD
Learning rate	10^{-1} , 10^{-2} , 10^{-3} , 10^{-4} , 10^{-5} , 10^{-6}

On the other hand, the LR will be modified using values in the range $\{10^{-1}, 10^{-2}, \dots, 10^{-6}\}$ and following a logarithmic scale. As mentioned in Section 3, there are some hyperparameters, such as the loss function and the batch size, that will not be considered in the training process of the hybrid ResNet50 CNN model and, consequently, will be maintained constant. Categorical cross-entropy (CCE) has been chosen as the loss function. As for the batch size, although it was mentioned in Section 3.3 that this is a hyperparameter that can be adjusted, it has not been considered as an input variable for the proposed grid search. The main reason is that the available memory on the GPU only allows processing a maximum of 9 images at a time. This value is not high enough to compromise the performance of the model but allows faster training than lower values. Therefore, the batch size has been set to 9 for this model. As mentioned previously, other aspects of the grid search like the number and type of layers, the size of the filters, the activation function (ReLU in this case), the pooling strategy or the rate of the dropout algorithm of the original ResNet50 model could also have been modified in addition to the aforementioned hyperparameters. However, since the commercial CNN model is being used to perform the defect classification task, this will not be done, leaving possible modifications to the network architecture for future work. The best configuration for the model will be

selected in accordance with the grid search hyperparameters. Early stopping conditions have also been established so that if the validation loss does not improve over ten consecutive iterations, the training of the model is stopped. Therefore, the grid search model of the hybrid ResNet50 CNN is trained with each of the parameter combinations with the objective to locate the optimal set of hyperparameters which will be used to classify more accurately the different defects in semiconductor wafers. The settings in terms of the optimizer and the LR, as well as the F1-score and the validation loss for each combination are collected in Table 6.

Table 6: Grid search results for the proposed hybrid ResNet50 Model.

Configuration	Optimizer	LR	F1-score	Validation loss
1	ADAM	10^{-1}	0.96134	0.11098
2	SGD	10^{-1}	0.98985	0.03726
3	ADAM	10^{-2}	0.99004	0.16274
4	SGD	10^{-2}	0.99443	0.03031
6	SGD	10^{-3}	0.99426	0.03392
7	ADAM	10^{-4}	0.99340	0.02292
9	ADAM	10^{-5}	0.68958	0.07537
10	SGD	10^{-5}	0.10939	0.61068
11	ADAM	10^{-6}	0.17715	0.44126
12	SGD	10^{-6}	0.04058	1.15308

From Table 6 it is observed that the SGD optimizer obtains slightly better results than ADAM for the majority of LRs. On the other hand, regarding the LR, values between 10^{-1} and 10^{-2} , offers the best results. The optimal settings, which are highlighted in Table 6, are those which include SGD as the optimizer and a LR with a value of 10^{-2} , obtaining a F1-score value of 0.99443 and a validation loss value of 0.03031. Finally, in order to illustrate, the tuning evolution of the proposed hybrid CNN model, learning curves are provided which are depicted in Figure 8 showing that, at first glance, the results are quite impressive. As the F1-score suggests, the classification performance of the model is really good and, as far as loss is concerned, it is negligible. The training curves are also correct. Accuracy and loss fluctuate throughout the first few epochs. However, after the tenth epoch, both curves tend to converge smoothly. [It should also be noted that a lower number of images, or images of lower quality, or noisy images, would have led to worse classification results.](#) Finally, although the results are indeed

promising, they need to be compared with those obtained by other state-of-the-art commercial CNN models to draw fully meaningful conclusions.

Figure 8: Training curves of the proposed hybrid CNN model.

4.2. Comparison With Other State-of-the-Art CNN Models

In this case, two powerful and worldwide used CNN models such as InceptionV3 and EfficientNet-B0 have been selected to perform a comparative study with the hybrid deep residual neural network proposed in this research when working with an imbalanced dataset. Both CNN are briefly presented next.

- *Inception V3* is an example of an Inception network [74], whose architecture is depicted in Figure 9. Inception networks, which owe their name to the use of inception modules, introduce two major advantages in the CNN field [74]: (i) a significant reduction in the volume of data that the network must deal with, and, (ii) the use of inception modules, which permit performing several convolution operations in parallel, allows the use of different kernel sizes for the same layer. Regarding the pooling strategy, Inception networks combine maximum pooling and average pooling, with ReLU generally being the activation function used. Inception networks have evolved from the primitive InceptionV1, which has a depth of 22 convolutional layers, to InceptionV3 whose depth is 42 [75].

Figure 9: InceptionV3 CNN architecture [76].

- *EfficientNet-B0* emerged back in 2019 with the aim of solving the scaling problems of the state-of-the-art of CNN models [77] and whose architecture is shown in Figure 10. By that time, network scaling was carried out by means of three different approaches, applied in an individual manner [77]: (i) increasing the depth (higher number of layers); (ii) increasing the width (more channels); and, (iii) working with image resolution. Then, EfficientNet-B0 introduced a compound scaling, where three different constants, determined through a grid search, and a fourth parameter configured by the user in order to adapt the network to the equipment’s capacities were set to perform the scaling of the network. From a base model, EfficientNet-B0 is composed of an input convolutional layer, seven mobile inverted bottleneck blocks (Mobile Block (MB) Convolution) and a fully-connected (FC) layer. The pooling strategy in these networks involves the use of global average pooling, while the Swish activation function is employed in the activation layers. The rest of the EfficientNet models (ranging from 1 to 7) are obtained by means of this compound scaling operation [35, 78].

Both CNNs, InceptionV3 and EfficientNet-B0, are presumably efficient and powerful, making them perfect for assessing a comparative study in terms of performance with the proposed hybrid model presented in this research when working with imbalanced datasets. The fine tuning of the hybrid EfficientNet-B0 and hybrid InceptionV3 CNN models is done in the same manner as for the proposed hybrid deep residual neural network, hybrid ResNet50 CNN model. The grid search hyperparameter combinations

Figure 10: EfficientNet-B0 CNN architecture [79].

previously considered were set to train the aforementioned models and the optimal set of hyperparameters were chosen based on the values of the F1-score and the validation loss metrics. The only difference was in the value of the batch size hyperparameter, which was set to a value of 2 based for the hybrid InceptionV3 model and to a value of 9 for the hybrid EfficientNet-B0 model, following the same criteria as for the ResNet50 model, since these values correspond to the maximum number of images that the GPU can process at a time, and are not high enough to negatively affect the performance of the model. Once again, remaining faithful to the original architecture of both networks, the number and type of layers, the number of filters, the pooling strategy, the activation function and other parameters such as the dropout rate will not be modified in the grid search.

The comparative optimal settings obtained for all the hybrid CNN models considered in terms of the optimizer and the LR hyperparameters, together with the corresponding values of the metrics F1-score, the Cohen’s kappa (κ) coefficient and the validation loss for each of the CNN models considered are resumed in Table 7 where it is noted that the best optimizer for the three hybrid CNN models is SGD. On the other hand, regarding the LR, the use of values between 10^{-1} and 10^{-2} offers the best results. Finally, it can be clearly seen that, although the results in terms of F1-score, κ coefficient and validation loss are quite similar for the three hybrid CNN models, the proposed hybrid CNN model achieves the highest F1-score and the highest κ coefficient. In other words, the performance of the proposed hybrid CNN model is the best in classification according to the two metrics used for evaluation. Another metric that may be really helpful, not only for evaluating the performance of the models, but also for clearly and easily visualizing the results is the confusion matrix.

Figure 11 shows the confusion matrices of the three hybrid CNN models. If an element in the diagonal of the different matrices is shaded in dark blue,

Table 7: Tuned hybrid CNN models

CNN Model	Optimizer	LR	F1-score	κ	Validation loss
Hybrid InceptionV3	SGD	10^{-1}	0.99244	0.98277	0.09060
Hybrid ResNet50	SGD	10^{-2}	0.99443	0.98708	0.03031
Hybrid EfficientNet-B0	SGD	10^{-1}	0.99024	0.97848	0.04460

it means that this model achieves the same classification performance as the proposed hybrid CNN model for that class. Conversely, if the element is shaded in red, it means that the model performs worse than the ResNet50 CNN model. Lastly, a green color means that the model outperforms the proposed CNN model. Moreover, Figure 11 shows that the InceptionV3 CNN model only outperforms our proposed model in the classification of Class 150, while it performs worse in Classes 100 and 350. Regarding the hybrid EfficientNet-B0 CNN model, it performs worse than the hybrid ResNet50 CNN model in the classification of Classes 100 and 300. However, despite the few differences between the results achieved by the different models, the results are really promising. The hybrid InceptionV3 CNN model classifies correctly 546 out of the 550 defects that compose the test set, the hybrid ResNet50 classifies properly 547 out of the 550 defects, and the hybrid EfficientNet-B0 CNN model achieves 545 out of 550. It is interesting to remark that the minority classes were classified in a successful manner.

Figure 11: Confusion matrices comparison between the hybrid CNN models.

Finally, apart from the classification results, it is crucial to bear in mind the computing time. Not every model takes the same time in training. A comparison between the computing time of the three hybrid CNN models is

presented in Table 8 where it is observed that the hybrid InceptionV3 CNN model requires the longest training time, while the hybrid ResNet50 and the hybrid EfficientNet-B0 CNN models need a similar training time. The difference between the number of epochs is due to the early stopping conditions. The hybrid ResNet50 CNN model only invests 22 epochs for its training (stabilizes earlier than the others). Therefore, once analyzed the presented results for each of the models, it can be seen that both hybrid EfficientNet-B0 and hybrid ResNet50 perform similarly both in terms of classification and computing time, while hybrid InceptionV3 achieves comparable classification results despite the consumption of additional training time. However, hybrid ResNet50 CNN model slightly outperforms the other state-of-the-art models, proving that the final tuned model is an optimal tool to carry out the defect detection and classification tasks.

Table 8: Computing time comparison between the hybrid CNN models.

CNN model	Time per epoch (s)	Number of epochs	Total time (h)
Hybrid InceptionV3	246	34	2.323
Hybrid ResNet50	202	22	1.234
Hybrid EfficientNet-B0	188	29	1.514

4.3. Comparison with Related Recent Research Works

It is well known that comparisons with other research works, even if those operate with similar images (SEM) and models, are tricky. The fact is that the complexity of each task differs from the rest, leading to very different classification results. Nevertheless, the results obtained in this work should be compared with those obtained in similar approaches. Table 9 collects the comparative results between the proposed research developed in this work and several related research works obtained from the most up-to-date scientific literature.

For example, a CNN model has been developed in [20] to classify five different types of surface defects on semiconductor wafers. This model achieves an accuracy of 0.987, which is comparable to that achieved by the models discussed in our research. However, it is note that, although the data set used by the authors contains significantly fewer images (2,123), the model proposed by the authors takes much longer to train. This is probably due to the use of a CPU instead of a GPU for training.

In [23], different state-of-the-art CNN predesigned models are tested with the aim of classifying eleven different defect classes. The authors compare

Table 9: Comparison with related works.

Reference	CNN model	F1-score	Accuracy	Computing time
[20]	Chien’s design	—	0.987	42,856 s
	VGG16	0.840	0.844	—
	ResNet50	0.872	0.875	—
[23]	InceptionResNetV2	0.886	0.900	—
	R-VGG16	0.899	0.960	—
	R-ResNet50	0.906	0.986	—
	R-InceptionResNetV2	0.909	0.974	—
[25]	O’Leary’s design	—	0.821	0.264 seconds/defect/epoch/GPU
	Hybrid InceptionV3	0.992	0.993	8,364 s
This work	Hybrid ResNet50	0.994	0.995	4,444 s
	Hybrid EfficientNet-B0	0.990	0.991	5,452 s

the predesigned models with the same models but applying the so-called Radon transform for the first feature extraction. The results achieved by the models that apply the Radon transform are promising. However, there is no information regarding the computing time and the original dataset. Therefore, a thorough comparison is hard to be made.

Finally, in [25], the authors developed a CNN model and merged the output with the data coming from an energy dispersive X-Ray (EDX) device to classify the chemical composition of particle defects on the surface of semiconductor wafers, achieving a top-1 accuracy of 0.821 and a top-3 accuracy of 0.992, which are great results as the task is much more complicated. The original dataset contained 5,859 SEM images from nine different classes.

On the other hand, regarding the comparative study in terms of computing time, it is difficult to discuss if there is lack of information in the studied papers. The fact is that, as the complexity of the tasks is different, it is difficult to compare the results obtained by the authors with the results presented in this research.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, a hybrid CNN-grid search-based deep residual neural network is developed that automatically classifies various types of defects in semiconductor wafers from SEM images. The proposed model merges traditional computer vision techniques to perform defect segmentation and a CNN model. Since the dataset of SEM images is highly imbalanced, a synthetic image generation process needs to be implemented based on image

transformations (scaling, rotation, flipping and translation) of the original images with the aim to improve the accuracy of the classification process. On the other hand, a ResNet50 CNN model has been used as deep residual neural network which is optimally tuned by means of a grid search algorithm. Among the main characteristics of the proposed model, the following should be mentioned: (i) the grid search algorithm has been incorporated to the proposed hybrid model as hyperparameter optimization technique to minimize the predefined losses and to improve the accuracy of the classification model; (ii) the parameters considered for evaluation are F1-score, κ , confusion matrix and computation time.

The proposed model outperforms all the other baseline algorithms with an accuracy greater than 99.443% while consuming the least computation time; (iii) the hyperparameter tuning leads to an increase in the model performance; (iv) the proposed hybrid model reports better accuracy in classification with respect to other baseline algorithms (see Tables 7 and 8, and Figure 11); and, (v) after carrying out a comparative study between the proposed hybrid model and recent works on defect detection and classification in semiconductor wafers from SEM images, the study reports that the proposed research presents the best performance (see Table 9).

About future works, there are several research lines that remain opened after concluding this research article. These are the following: (i) continuing with the same line of research, lightweight CNN models such as SqueezeNet [80] could compete with the heavy commercial models tested in this work for the proposed application. It should be noted that not only classification performance, but also training time is crucial in a fast-changing semiconductor industry, where models must be retrained from time to time as new defects arise from changes in tools and materials, among others [81]. This is where lightweight models as SqueezeNet could find a niche in this powerful industry; (ii) a genetic algorithm could be applied to create a self-designed model that fits the best to the described task; (iii) data augmentation analysis could be performed in order to find the optimal number of synthetic images needed to achieve the best classification result for our particular task; (iv) the use of generative adversarial networks (GAN) may be introduced for data augmentation purposes. Software such as PyTorch [82] includes options to fine tune this kind of models in order to generate realistic images. A comparison between the results obtained with GAN and those obtained with traditional techniques could be interesting; and, (v) a combination of ML and DL models could be tested to deal with unknown classes. This is a problem that has

been faced on multiple occasions without obtaining a general solution. As just mentioned above, the industry environment is noisy and unpredictable. As a result, new defects can appear, and the models should be prepared to classify them as *unknown*. Designing a model with these abilities is a challenge to be studied in a near future.

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations have been used in this manuscript:

ACR	Accuracy
ACR _e	Agreement between the actual class values and the model predictions by chance
ACR _o	Overall accuracy of the model
ADAM	Adaptive moment estimation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CCE	Categorical cross-entropy
CNN	Convolutional neural network
DL	Deep learning
EDX	Energy dispersive X-ray
F1	F1-score
FC	Fully-connected
FN	False negative
FP	False positive
GAN	Generative adversarial network
GPU	Graphics processing unit
IDE	Integrated development environment
κ	Cohen's kappa coefficient
K-NN	K-nearest neighbors
LaB ₆	Lanthanum hexaboride
LR	Learning rate
MB	Mobile block
ML	Machine learning
OVR	One-versus-the-rest
P	Precision
R	Recall
RB	Residual block
ReLU	Rectified linear unit
ResNet	Residual network
SEM	Scanning electron microscope
SGD	Stochastic gradient descent
TN	True negative
TP	True positive

Declarations

- a. *Funding.* This work was partially supported by iRel40, a European co-funded innovation project that has been granted by the ECSEL Joint Undertaking (JU) (grant number 876659). The funding of the project comes from the Horizon 2020 research programme and participating countries. National funding is provided by Germany, including the Free States of Saxony and Thuringia, Austria, Belgium, Finland, France, Italy, the Netherlands, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, and Turkey. Grant PCI2020-112001 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by the European Union “NextGenerationEU” / PRTR.
- b. *Conflicts of interest/Competing interests.* The authors declare no conflicts of interest/competing interests.
- c. *Availability of data and material.* Will be made available upon request.
- d. *Code availability.* Will be made available upon request.
- e. *Ethics approval.* The authors confirm that the submitted work is original and has not been published elsewhere.
- f. *Consent to participate.* Not applicable for this paper.
- g. *Consent for publication.* Not applicable for this paper.
- h. *Authors’ contributions.* All authors contributed to the study conception, design and experimental validation. The first draft of the manuscript was written by all authors. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

References

- [1] B. Foucher, J. Boullie, B. Meslet, D. Das, A review of reliability prediction methods for electronic devices, *Microelectronics Reliability* 42 (8) (2002) 1155–1162.
- [2] M. A. Farsi, E. Zio, Industry 4.0: some challenges and opportunities for reliability engineering, *International Journal of Reliability, Risk and Safety: Theory and Application* 2 (1) (2019) 23–34.
- [3] Q. Ahmed, S. A. Raza, D. M. Al-Anazi, Reliability-based fault analysis models with industrial applications: a systematic literature review, *Quality and Reliability Engineering International* 37 (4) (2021) 1307–1333.

- [4] STATISTA, Monthly semiconductor sales worldwide from 2012 to 2020 (in billion u.s. dollars) (2019).
URL <https://www.statista.com/statistics/277404/global-semiconductor-sales-by->
- [5] C.-F. Chien, C.-C. Chen, Adaptive parametric yield enhancement via collinear multivariate analytics for semiconductor intelligent manufacturing, *Applied Soft Computing* 108 (2021) 107385.
- [6] A. Jain, J. G. Sheridan, R. Xing, F. Levitov, S. Yasharzade, H. Nguyen, SEM imaging and automated defect analysis at advanced technology nodes, in: 2017 28th Annual SEMI Advanced Semiconductor Manufacturing Conference (ASMC), IEEE, 2017, pp. 240–8. doi:10.23919/mipro.2017.7966585.
- [7] S. Halder, D. Cerbu, M. Saib, P. Leray, Sem image analysis with k-means algorithm: Am: Advanced metrology/di: Defect inspection, in: 2018 29th Annual SEMI Advanced Semiconductor Manufacturing Conference (ASMC), IEEE, 2018, pp. 255–258.
- [8] W. C. J. Tam, R. D. S. Blanton, Lasic: Layout analysis for systematic ic-defect identification using clustering, *IEEE Transactions on Computer-Aided Design of Integrated Circuits and Systems* 34 (8) (2015) 1278–1290.
- [9] S. Purandare, J. Zhu, R. Zhou, G. Popescu, A. Schwing, L. L. Goddard, Optical inspection of nanoscale structures using a novel machine learning based synthetic image generation algorithm, *Optics express* 27 (13) (2019) 17743–17762.
- [10] J. L. Gómez-Sirvent, F. López de la Rosa, R. Sánchez-Reolid, A. Fernández-Caballero, R. Morales, Optimal feature selection for defect classification in semiconductor wafers, *IEEE Transactions on Semiconductor Manufacturing* (2022).
- [11] J. L. Gómez-Sirvent, F. L. de la Rosa, R. Sánchez-Reolid, R. Morales, A. Fernández-Caballero, Defect classification on semiconductor wafers using fisher vector and visual vocabularies coding, *Measurement* (2022) 111872.

- [12] P. H. Yeow, R. Nath Sen, Ergonomics improvements of the visual inspection process in a printed circuit assembly factory, *International Journal of Occupational Safety and Ergonomics* 10 (4) (2004) 369–385.
- [13] W. Dai, D. Li, D. Tang, Q. Jiang, D. Wang, H. Wang, Y. Peng, Deep learning assisted vision inspection of resistance spot welds, *Journal of Manufacturing Processes* 62 (2021) 262–274.
- [14] K. Y. Chan, K. F. C. Yiu, H.-K. Lam, B. W. Wong, Ball bonding inspections using a conjoint framework with machine learning and human judgement, *Applied Soft Computing* 102 (2021) 107115.
- [15] E. N. Malamas, E. G. Petrakis, M. Zervakis, L. Petit, J.-D. Legat, A survey on industrial vision systems, applications and tools, *Image and Vision Computing* 21 (2) (2003) 171–188.
- [16] J. Kim, Y. Nam, M. Kang, K. Kim, J. Hong, S. Lee, D.-N. Kim, Adversarial defect detection in semiconductor manufacturing process, *IEEE Transactions on Semiconductor Manufacturing* (2021).
- [17] B.-S. Lin, J.-S. Cheng, H.-C. Liao, L.-W. Yang, T. Yang, K.-C. Chen, Improvement of multi lines bridge defect classification by hierarchical architecture in artificial intelligence automatic defect classification, *IEEE Transactions on Semiconductor Manufacturing* (2021).
- [18] A. Krizhevsky, I. Sutskever, G. E. Hinton, Imagenet classification with deep convolutional neural networks, *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* 25 (2012) 1097–1105.
- [19] H. Lei, C. Teh, H. Li, P.-H. Lee, W. Fang, Automated wafer defect classification using a convolutional neural network augmented with distributed computing, in: *2020 31st Annual SEMI Advanced Semiconductor Manufacturing Conference (ASMC)*, IEEE, 2020, pp. 1–5.
- [20] S. Cheon, H. Lee, C. O. Kim, S. H. Lee, Convolutional neural network for wafer surface defect classification and the detection of unknown defect class, *IEEE Transactions on Semiconductor Manufacturing* 32 (2) (2019) 163–170.

- [21] L. Wang, L. Zhang, X. Qi, Z. Yi, Deep attention-based imbalanced image classification, *IEEE transactions on neural networks and learning systems* (2021).
- [22] C.-T. Su, T. Yang, C.-M. Ke, A neural-network approach for semiconductor wafer post-sawing inspection, *IEEE Transactions on Semiconductor Manufacturing* 15 (2) (2002) 260–266.
- [23] Y. Yuan-Fu, S. Min, Double feature extraction method for wafer map classification based on convolution neural network, in: 2020 31st Annual SEMI Advanced Semiconductor Manufacturing Conference (ASMC), IEEE, 2020, pp. 1–6.
- [24] G. Beylkin, Discrete radon transform, *IEEE transactions on acoustics, speech, and signal processing* 35 (2) (1987) 162–172.
- [25] J. O’Leary, K. Sawlani, A. Mesbah, Deep learning for classification of the chemical composition of particle defects on semiconductor wafers, *IEEE Transactions on Semiconductor Manufacturing* 33 (1) (2020) 72–85.
- [26] X. Zheng, S. Zheng, Y. Kong, J. Chen, Recent advances in surface defect inspection of industrial products using deep learning techniques, *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology* 113 (1) (2021) 35–58.
- [27] C. Shorten, T. M. Khoshgoftaar, A survey on image data augmentation for deep learning, *Journal of Big Data* 6 (1) (2019) 1–48.
- [28] M. Hossin, M. N. Sulaiman, A review on evaluation metrics for data classification evaluations, *International Journal of Data Mining & Knowledge Management Process* 5 (2) (2015) 1.
- [29] W. Zhou, R. Apkarian, Z. L. Wang, D. Joy, Fundamentals of scanning electron microscopy (sem), in: *Scanning Microscopy for Nanotechnology*, Springer, 2006, pp. 1–40.
- [30] J. Zhang, H. Zhang, J. Wu, J. Zhang, Chapter 11 - fuel cell degradation and failure analysis, in: J. Zhang, H. Zhang, J. Wu, J. Zhang (Eds.), *Pem Fuel Cell Testing and Diagnosis*, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 2013, pp. 283–335. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-53688-4.00011-5>.

- [31] K. Graff, Scanning Electron Microscope (2018).
URL <https://pixels.com/featured/scanning-electron-microscope-karl-gaff--scien>
- [32] K. Vernon-Parry, Scanning electron microscopy: an introduction, *III-Vs Review* 13 (4) (2000) 40–44.
- [33] M. Kannan, Scanning electron microscopy: Principle, components and applications, *A Textbook on Fundamentals and Applications of Nanotechnology* (2018) 81–92.
- [34] B. Hafner, Scanning electron microscopy primer, Characterization Facility, University of Minnesota-Twin Cities (2007) 1–29.
- [35] F. López de la Rosa, R. Sánchez-Reolid, J. L. Gómez-Sirvent, R. Morales, A. Fernández-Caballero, A review on machine and deep learning for semiconductor defect classification in scanning electron microscope images, *Applied Sciences* 11 (20) (2021) 9508.
- [36] H. Zheng, S. W. A. Sherazi, S. H. Son, J. Y. Lee, A deep convolutional neural network-based multi-class image classification for automatic wafer map failure recognition in semiconductor manufacturing, *Applied Sciences* 11 (20) (2021) 9769.
- [37] X. Tao, D. Zhang, W. Hou, W. Ma, D. Xu, Industrial weak scratches inspection based on multifeature fusion network, *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement* 70 (2020) 1–14.
- [38] P.-C. Shih, C.-C. Hsu, F.-C. Tien, Automatic reclaimed wafer classification using deep learning neural networks, *Symmetry* 12 (5) (2020) 705.
- [39] Z. Li, Practice of gesture recognition based on resnet50, *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* 1574 (1) (2020) 012154. doi:10.1088/1742-6596/1574/1/012154.
- [40] K. Fukushima, Neocognitron: A hierarchical neural network capable of visual pattern recognition, *Neural Networks* 1 (2) (1988) 119–130.
- [41] N. Ketkar, Convolutional neural networks, in: *Deep Learning with Python*, Springer, 2017, pp. 63–78.

- [42] H. Leung, S. Haykin, The complex backpropagation algorithm, *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing* 39 (9) (1991) 2101–2104.
- [43] K. O’Shea, R. Nash, An introduction to convolutional neural networks, *ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:1511.08458* (2015).
- [44] R. H. Hahnloser, R. Sarpeshkar, M. A. Mahowald, R. J. Douglas, H. S. Seung, Digital selection and analogue amplification coexist in a cortex-inspired silicon circuit, *Nature* 405 (6789) (2000) 947–951.
- [45] N. Aloysius, M. Geetha, A review on deep convolutional neural networks, in: *2017 international conference on communication and signal processing (ICCSP)*, IEEE, 2017, pp. 0588–0592.
- [46] K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, J. Sun, Spatial pyramid pooling in deep convolutional networks for visual recognition, *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence* 37 (9) (2015) 1904–1916.
- [47] M. D. Zeiler, R. Fergus, Stochastic pooling for regularization of deep convolutional neural networks, *ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:1301.3557* (2013).
- [48] O. Rippel, J. Snoek, R. P. Adams, Spectral representations for convolutional neural networks, *ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:1506.03767* (2015).
- [49] Y. Gong, L. Wang, R. Guo, S. Lazebnik, Multi-scale orderless pooling of deep convolutional activation features, in: *European Conference on Computer Vision*, Springer, 2014, pp. 392–407.
- [50] A. Zafar, M. Aamir, N. Mohd Nawi, A. Arshad, S. Riaz, A. Alruban, A. K. Dutta, S. Almotairi, A comparison of pooling methods for convolutional neural networks, *Applied Sciences* 12 (17) (2022) 8643.
- [51] S. Sharma, R. Mehra, Implications of pooling strategies in convolutional neural networks: A deep insight, *Foundations of Computing and Decision Sciences* 44 (3) (2019) 303–330.
- [52] S. Bera, V. K. Shrivastava, Effect of pooling strategy on convolutional neural network for classification of hyperspectral remote sensing images, *IET Image Processing* 14 (3) (2020) 480–486.

- [53] L. Liu, C. Shen, A. Van Den Hengel, The treasure beneath convolutional layers: Cross-convolutional-layer pooling for image classification, in: Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 2015, pp. 4749–4757.
- [54] S. S. Basha, S. R. Dubey, V. Pulabaigari, S. Mukherjee, Impact of fully connected layers on performance of convolutional neural networks for image classification, *Neurocomputing* 378 (2020) 112–119.
- [55] P. Baldi, P. J. Sadowski, Understanding dropout, *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* 26 (2013) 2814–2822.
- [56] K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, J. Sun, Deep residual learning for image recognition, in: Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 2016, pp. 770–778.
- [57] M. Farnsworth, D. Tiwari, Z. Zhang, G. W. Jewell, A. Tiwari, Augmented classification for electrical coil winding defects, *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology* (2022) 1–17.
- [58] J. Utrera, Deep Learning básico con Keras (Parte 4): ResNet (2018).
URL <https://enmilocalfunciona.io/deep-learning-basico-con-keras-parte-4-resnet>
- [59] F. López de la Rosa, J. L. Gómez-Sirvent, R. Sánchez-Reolid, R. Morales, A. Fernández-Caballero, Geometric transformation-based data augmentation on defect classification of segmented images of semiconductor materials using a resnet50 convolutional neural network, *Expert Systems with Applications* (2022) 117731.
- [60] C. Xia, Z. Pan, Z. Fei, S. Zhang, H. Li, Vision based defects detection for keyhole tig welding using deep learning with visual explanation, *Journal of Manufacturing Processes* 56 (2020) 845–855.
- [61] P. Baheti, Train Test Validation Split: How To Best Practices [2022] (2022).
URL <https://www.v7labs.com/blog/train-validation-test-set>
- [62] P. Liashchynskiy, P. Liashchynskiy, Grid search, random search, genetic algorithm: a big comparison for nas, *ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:1912.06059* (2019).

- [63] F. Hutter, L. Kotthoff, J. Vanschoren, Automated machine learning: methods, systems, challenges, Springer Nature, 2019.
- [64] D. P. Kingma, J. Ba, Adam: A method for stochastic optimization, ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:1412.6980 (2014).
- [65] H. Robbins, S. Monro, A stochastic approximation method, The Annals of Mathematical Statistics (1951) 400–407.
- [66] N. Japkowicz, Assessment metrics for imbalanced learning, Imbalanced learning: Foundations, algorithms, and applications (2013) 187–206.
- [67] R. Sánchez-Reolid, M. T. López, A. Fernández-Caballero, Machine learning for stress detection from electrodermal activity: A scoping review, Preprints (2020).
- [68] R. Cruz, K. Fernandes, J. S. Cardoso, J. F. P. Costa, Tackling class imbalance with ranking, in: 2016 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN), IEEE, 2016, pp. 2182–2187.
- [69] J. Cohen, A coefficient of agreement for nominal scales, Educational and Psychological Measurement 20 (1) (1960) 37–46.
- [70] Keras, Keras: the Python deep learning API (2022).
URL <https://keras.io/>
- [71] TensorFlow, An end-to-end machine learning platform (2022).
URL <https://www.tensorflow.org/>
- [72] JetBrains s.r.o., The Python IDE for Professional Developers (2022).
URL <https://www.jetbrains.com/pycharm/>
- [73] Python Software Foundation, Welcome to Python.org (2016).
URL <https://www.python.org/> <https://www.python.org/about/>
- [74] C. Szegedy, W. Liu, Y. Jia, P. Sermanet, S. Reed, D. Anguelov, D. Erhan, V. Vanhoucke, A. Rabinovich, Going deeper with convolutions, in: Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 2015, pp. 1–9.

- [75] C. Szegedy, V. Vanhoucke, S. Ioffe, J. Shlens, Z. Wojna, Rethinking the inception architecture for computer vision, in: Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition, 2016, pp. 2818–2826.
- [76] J. Shlens, Train your own image classifier with Inception in TensorFlow (2016).
URL <https://ai.googleblog.com/2016/03/train-your-own-image-classifier-with.html>
- [77] M. Tan, Q. Le, Efficientnet: Rethinking model scaling for convolutional neural networks, in: International Conference on Machine Learning, PMLR, 2019, pp. 6105–6114.
- [78] M. Sandler, A. Howard, M. Zhu, A. Zhmoginov, L.-C. Chen, Mobilenetv2: Inverted residuals and linear bottlenecks, in: Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 2018, pp. 4510–4520.
- [79] M. Tan, Q. Le, EfficientNet: Improving Accuracy and Efficiency through AutoML and Model Scaling (2019).
URL <https://ai.googleblog.com/2019/05/efficientnet-improving-accuracy-and.html>
- [80] F. N. Iandola, S. Han, M. W. Moskewicz, K. Ashraf, W. J. Dally, K. Keutzer, Squeezenet: Alexnet-level accuracy with 50x fewer parameters and 0.5 mb model size, arXiv preprint arXiv:1602.07360 (2016).
- [81] F. López de la Rosa, J. L. Gómez-Sirvent, C. Kofler, R. Morales, A. Fernández-Caballero, Detection of unknown defects in semiconductor materials from a hybrid deep and machine learning approach, in: J. M. Ferrández Vicente, J. R. Álvarez-Sánchez, F. de la Paz López, H. Adeli (Eds.), Bio-inspired Systems and Applications: from Robotics to Ambient Intelligence, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2022, pp. 356–365.
- [82] Pytorch, An open source machine learning framework that accelerates the path from research prototyping to production deployment. (2022).
URL <https://pytorch.org/>